

MODERN NEW GENERATION DEVICES IN COMPUTER TOMOGRAPHY. DENTOPR APPARATUS CAPABLE OF SIMULTANEOUSLY VISUALIZING BOTH SOFT AND HARD TISSUES

S.A. Abdurakhmonov¹, Sh.Sh. Esanov², A.Sh. Ulugberdiyev³, J.T. Abdurazzoqov⁴
Tashkent Medical Academy^{1,2,3,4}

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Abstract. Modern medical technology, such as Multislice Computed Tomography (MSCT), is highly effective in diagnosing diseases like cancer, cardiovascular diseases, infectious diseases, musculoskeletal system injuries, and musculoskeletal system diseases. However, its use in diagnosing the facial-jaw area can lead to the development of tumor diseases in patients. Therefore, in dentistry, particularly for diagnosing the facial-jaw area, the Dento Proprietas X-ray device, which is based on the working principle of MSCT, is considered. The absence of requirements placed on patients during the diagnostic process compensates for the shortcomings of previous diagnostic devices.

Keywords: dento Proprietas X-ray, Multislice Computed Tomography, stationary detectors, X-ray tube, diagnostics, scanning, hard and soft tissues.

Currently, computer diagnostics play a crucial role in modern medicine. Specifically, Multislice Computed Tomography (MSCT) provides a versatile non-invasive imaging method suitable for evaluating the anatomy of adolescents or elderly patients with complex diseases. In the first 10 years of its development, only projection methods, radiography, angiographic-planar scintigraphy were used. Technical progress and the advent of computers led to the development of tomographic methods, which today occupy a leading position in radiation diagnostics. The starting point for the development of radiation diagnostic methods was the emergence of computed tomography (CT). The creation of CT is comparable in its importance to the discovery of X-rays. In 1998, another stage in the development of CT appeared - multispiral CT (MSCT). This is a type of computed tomography and is one of the most modern methods for viewing organs and tissues. MSCT is capable of diagnosing conditions such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, infectious diseases, musculoskeletal system injuries, hemorrhages in organs and tissues, and diseases of the musculoskeletal system. The main idea of MSCT is to use multiple rows of detectors alongside expanding the X-ray beams in the z-direction to make more efficient use of X-rays. This enables the collection of multiple images simultaneously. Additionally, in terms of visualizing bone tissue quality, MSCT surpasses MRI. However, like all modern medical technologies, MSCT also has its own requirements and limitations:

The harmful effects of ionizing X-rays are always present. The dose of radiation received during research is equivalent to the dose an average person would receive from environmental background radiation over several years.

Pregnancy is a definite contraindication for MSCT and should only be performed for health reasons.

Breastfeeding mothers should avoid feeding their baby for 24 hours after the introduction of a contrast agent.

There is a risk of severe allergic reactions to contrast agents containing iodine.

Additionally, MSCT is not suitable for patients with a body weight exceeding 120 kg (due to the technical specifications of the tomography), those with inadequate mental capacity and psychiatric disorders, immobility, severe pain, or hyperkinesia.

Due to the aforementioned limitations, this device, which plays an important role in the medical field, affects patients differently during the diagnostic process, and these effects manifest in harmful ways. As medicine advances, various approaches are emerging to address these issues. Diagnosing different parts of the head without affecting other organs of the body can be a positive solution to the problems that arise.

This method is mainly aimed at wide application in the field of dentistry. According to statistics, one out of every twenty patients with toothache suffers from tumor diseases. These diseases include organ-specific malignant mesenchymal tumors, osteosarcoma, adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, angiosarcoma, and odontogenic tumors.

Dento Proprietas (DentoPR) X-ray machine.

The proposed method uses the Dento Proprietas X-ray device for facial-jaw diagnosis, which can simultaneously visualize hard and soft tissues. **The Dento Proprietas X-ray** apparatus is used in maxillofacial surgery and is designed to view both soft and hard tissues at the same time. Due to its low harmfulness, it can be used in pregnant women, children under 14 years old, and patients weighing more than 120 kg. The device's structure is based on the design of MSCT.

The X-ray tube and detector rotate behind a circular screen. The conical X-ray tube and the assembly of stationary detectors achieve very high temporal resolution through the electromagnetic deflection of the electron beam within the device, designed to image fast-moving tomographs. In the device, the source and detector move in a spiral path relative to the object. In comparison to acquiring individual slices for a specific radiation dose, spiral scanning can achieve improved image clarity. The spiral beam trajectory is characterized by its pitch, which is the transmission distance along the scanning range during one gantry rotation, divided by the slice collimation. This forms cone-shaped X-ray beams, which describe a spiral trajectory relative to the object, while a two-dimensional detector array measures the object. The source and the detector array are mounted on a gantry. A voltage of 220V is reduced through a transformer and fed into the receiver board. During the diagnostic process, the patient is seated, and the DentoPR device is positioned at the jaw area of the head. Therefore, diagnosing with the DentoPR device prevents radiation exposure to other parts of the patient's body. The X-ray tube and detectors are mounted

in the inner rotating section of the measuring (circular) part. Given that the device is mainly used for head diagnostics, the number of detector arrays and the energy of the emitted X-rays are taken into account. This ensures minimal negative effects of X-ray exposure on patients. During the diagnostic process, the inner rotating part moves, and the image is displayed on the screen through the interface. This shows that the DentoPR device is much more efficient and less harmful for diagnosing the facial-jaw area compared to MSCT.

Conclusion. Multislice computed tomography (MSCT) is an alternative noninvasive imaging modality that is well suited for the assessment of the anatomy of adolescents or adults with complex diseases, with its many capabilities. The basic idea of MSCT is to use multiple arrays of detectors in combination with the expansion of the x-ray beam in the z-direction to make more efficient use of the x-ray beam. Multislice Computed Tomography (MSCT) is a crucial device in modern medicine for diagnosing diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, infectious diseases, musculoskeletal system injuries, hemorrhages in organs and tissues, and musculoskeletal system diseases. However, due to the shortcomings shown during the diagnostic process, this important medical device affects patients in different ways, and these effects can be harmful. In particular, many patients undergoing facial diagnostics in the field of dentistry have been diagnosed with tumor diseases. As a modern solution, the Dento Proprietas X-ray device, based on the MSCT working principle and capable of visualizing both hard and soft tissues in the facial-jaw diagnosis, is proposed. The simplicity of this method and the minimal requirements during the diagnostic process open the door to high-level service to patients and significant advancements in the medical field.

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